

Reproductive and Child Health Services: Socio-economic Determinants of its Utilization in Northeast India

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Reproductive and Child Health (RCH) Services are an essential service in the promotion of women and child health. Besides this, their services are of utmost significance in promoting a healthy society. This paper is an outcome of a study that was conducted with the objectives of understanding the organisation of RCH care services in Northeast India and to analyse the pattern of utilization of RCH care services in this region. In addition to this, an attempt was also made to examine the socio-economic determinants of RCH services utilization. It is this latter objective that is the main focus of this paper. A descriptive research design was adopted, using non-probability sampling method and non-proportional quota sampling, wherein the four states of Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya and Sikkim were identified for the study. Then one representative institution from each level of healthcare in each state was identified for the purpose of collecting information regarding how the RCH care services are organised and delivered to the people in these states. Besides this, multi-stage sampling was used to collect information from the users' perspective. A total of 800 households were surveyed. This paper tries to establish the fact that woman's education, husband's education, and family income continue to be very significant determinants in promoting an effective utilization of RCH care services. Besides religion and caste, other significant socio-economic indicators such as source of drinking water, type of housing, numbers of rooms, separate kitchen, type of fuel used for cooking, type of toilet were recorded to understand the socio-economic class and how they influence utilisation of RCH services. Significant RCH indicators such as pregnancy registration, ANC utilisation, IFA consumption, type and place of delivery, availing of JSY, PNC services were also studied.

Introduction

The Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) World Factbook, 2014, reports Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) in India at 43.19, while its neighbour China records it at 14.79. Both are developing nations. This contrasting figure should be adequate to serve as a wake-up call to our nation. If we compare the same figure with those of the two most developed nations,

namely, the United Kingdom and the United States, which records these figures at 4.44 and 6.17 respectively, it should unnerve us. In addition to this, in 2010, another unnerving fact is that the above source records the Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) at 200 in India, 37 in China, 12 in the U.K. and 21 in the U.S.

Regarding the All India picture, as per the Sample Registration System (SRS)

Report, 2011, advanced states like Delhi and Tamil Nadu record IMRs at 28 and 22. The same Report notes IMRs for the northeastern states of Assam (AS), Manipur (MN), Meghalaya (ML), and Sikkim (SK) at 55, 11, 52, and 26 respectively. Regarding MMR, SRS 2007-09 notes these figures at 97 for Tamil Nadu and 390 for Assam. It is unavailable for Delhi as well as the other three states as on September 30, 2012. IMR and MMR are indeed strong indicators of RCH and hence we need to get oriented towards their significance if we are to understand RCH in the correct perspective.

Need for a Holistic Approach

It has to be appreciated that reproductive health does not affect women alone; it is a family health and social issue as well. The International Conference on Population and Development, Programme of Action, 1994, had aptly defined Reproductive health as, "a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, in all matters relating to the reproductive system and its functions and processes".

The definition suggests that reproductive health encompasses: a) the ability to reproduce; b) freedom to control reproduction; c) the ability to go through pregnancy and childbirth safely, with successful maternal and infant survival outcomes; d) the ability to obtain information about and access to safe, effective and affordable methods of family planning; e) the ability to have a satisfying safe sex life, free from fear of pregnancy and disease; and f) the ability to minimize gynaecological diseases and risks throughout all stages

of life.

In our country several people continue to die due to causes which have their genesis in early childhood illnesses, inefficient and inadequate new-born care, and most importantly maternity and childbirth complications. These factors hamper their early growth and lifelong development. Inadequate management of pregnancy and child birth related complications owing to lack of antenatal care, financial difficulties, and ignorance is a huge challenge today. It is thus pertinent to look at the socio-economic differentials, accessibility, utilization pattern and factors affecting the utilization of RCH services.

**Table 1:
Health Infrastructure in Position**

Facilities	AS	MN	ML	SK
Sub-centre	4604	420	397	147
Primary Health Centre	975	80	109	24
Community Health Centre	109	16	29	2
Doctor at PHCs	1478	170	104	32
Obstetricians & Gynaecologist at CHCs	69	-	5	-
Health Worker/ ANM PHCs & Subcentres	8723	975	787	291
Nursing Staff at PHCs & CHCs	2795	574	414	24

The Northeast Context

Particular attention is called for in the Northeast as there are additional unique issues related to gender, culture, language, religious faiths, economic capability, and geography while accessing the modern public health services. This paper however looks at the four states of Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, and Sikkim. The study was conceptualised with the broad aim of understanding the health system

(particularly the provisioning of RCH services) in the Northeast region.

Study Design and Sampling

A descriptive research design was adopted, wherein after understanding the various levels of health facilities that provides RCH services in these four states, household surveys were conducted. This facilitated understanding the health seeking behaviour and also identify the factors that influence the accessibility and utilisation of RCH services.

The mixed sampling method has been used, where in, firstly, using non-probability sampling method and non-proportional quota sampling, the four states were identified for the study. Then one representative institution from each level of healthcare in each state was identified for the purpose of collecting information regarding how the RCH care services are organised and delivered to the people in these states. Besides this, multi-stage sampling was used to collect information from the users' perspective. In this case, firstly, purposive sampling using multi-purpose techniques (theory based, maximum variation, snowball and homogeneous) was used to identify sample districts in the four states. Two districts each were identified in all the states except in Cachar (it is already a relatively large district). From each district, a PHC was identified from which at least two urban communities and at least two rural communities each under it were again identified. A total of 800 households were thus surveyed. The households were identified and selected based on the criteria that the household should have a young mother with at least one living child who is below 5 years of

age, and a recall reference period of six months. The tool also had a section on unmarried women and data related to this were collected from 24 respondents in Manipur and 35 in Sikkim.

Socio-Economic Classification

All the respondents were classified into various socio-economic classes using an updated version of Kuppuswamy's socio-economic status scale (Ravikumar, Dudala & Rao, 2013). They are presented below.

Table 2: Socio-Economic Class

Facilities	Frequency	%
Upper	8	1.0
Upper Middle	218	27.3
Middle / lower Middle	339	42.4
Lower / Upper Lower	234	29.3
Lower	1	0.1
Total	800	100

As we can see from the above table, the least numbers of respondents belong to the lower most and upper most category. Middle and lower middle form the largest majority, followed by lower/upper lower. India is largely comprised of middle income and lower income groups and data also reflects such a scenario. This is a serious cause for concern in terms of accessibility and affordability, where India's healthcare spending is lagging behind other low and middle income countries thus resulting in huge out-of-pocket (OOP) expenditures. According to the World Bank, in 2000, the total healthcare expenditure for India was 4.4% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as compared to 5.3% in other low and middle income countries (LMIC). In 2010, the figure was 4% for India and

5.7% for the other LMICs. Regarding OOP, it was 67% (India) and 44% (LMIC) in 2000; with marginal declines in both cases at 61% and 37% respectively in 2010.

The above table shows the age group classification of the respondents. We can see that maximum numbers of respondents were covered within the age groups of 20 to 40 years in all the states. In terms of religion, the study covered maximum Hindus in all the three states (Assam - 99.5%, Manipur - 74.5%, Sikkim - 50.5%), except Meghalaya (21%). Christians were highest in Meghalaya -73%, followed by Sikkim - 48%. This is reflective of the religious dominance in these states. However, although the Muslim population covered in Manipur was higher than that in Assam, it is purely related to the selection of communities because Assam has a very large Muslim population in general. It is thus not reflective of religious distribution. As per Census 2011, the Muslim population in Assam forms over 34% of its total population.

Table 3: Age Group of Respondent

Age	AS	MN	ML	S K
	%	%	%	%
15-20	-	9.0	1.5	9.5
20-25	22.5	20.0	22.0	25.5
25-30	43.0	20.5	33.0	33.0
30-35	18.5	26.0	18.0	16.5
35-40	14.5	15.5	18.5	8.0
40-45	15.0	6.5	5.5	5.5
45-50	-	2.5	1.5	2.0
Total	100	100	100	100

Regarding caste, it is a known fact that the caste system is not a strong concern in the NER. However, in states like Assam, it has some significance. The other states being based on an aboriginal tribal culture, the caste system has not taken deep roots, unlike what we see in

the other parts of India. There were thus 35% SCs in Assam and only 8% in Sikkim. In Sikkim too, the caste system is practiced amongst the Nepalese. It was negligibly covered in the other two states as their presence is also rather low. ST presence was very high in Meghalaya (77%), followed by Sikkim (36%) and Manipur (13%). OBCs were again highest in Assam (48%), followed by Sikkim (41%). The general category population covered was highest in Manipur (85%). It was 17% in Assam, 18% in Meghalaya, and 16% in Sikkim. All the respondents were married except for 12% in Manipur and 18% in Sikkim, who were considered owing to situational and field issues.

Education

DLHS 2007-08 had concluded that non-literate women were less likely to be aware of family life education compared to women with ten or more years of education. Education is effective when it results in changes in one's knowledge, attitudes and practices (KAP). According to NFHS -3 (2005-06), mothers with no education and mothers in the lowest wealth quintile are twice as likely to lose their children in late pregnancy and during the first few days of life as mothers who have twelve or more years of education and mothers in the highest wealth quintile. In the patriarchal Indian society, the low status of women in the household indicates that health seeking behaviour of women in such a traditional society greatly depends on the decision of the partner or other older household members. In such a scenario, her own education will make a lot of difference in terms of awareness and decision making. Recent

studies show that status of women is an important determinant of maternal health (Mahapatro, 2012). Regarding education, the table below presents the details of this study.

Table 4: Level of Education

Education of the Respondents	AS	MN	ML	SK
Illiterate	24.5	8.5	11.5	8.5
Lower Primary	16.0	2.0	18.5	14.0
Upper Primary	9.5	9.5	15.0	27.0
High School	20.5	36	32.5	27.5
Higher Secondary	23.5	23.0	13.5	13.0
Graduation	5.5	16.5	8.5	8.0
Post-Graduation	0.5	4.5	0.5	2.0
Total	100	100	100	100

Family Education

Information was collected about the highest education attained by a member of each household that was surveyed. It was found that households with the highest numbers of post graduates are from Manipur, followed by Sikkim. Not surprisingly, RCH indicators are better in Manipur and Sikkim as compared to the other two states. DLHS 2007-08 had reported that any ANC is highest amongst women educated for ten years or more. This observation held constant across all these four states. According to reports, institutional deliveries in Assam increased by less than 7% during NFHS-2 and NFHS-3. In Meghalaya, it increased between 7-14%, while in Manipur and Sikkim, it increased by more than 15%. Thus this corroborates that education and RCH indicators are significantly related.

Husband's Education

Being better educated has been seen to play a strong role in determining the

type of healthcare one seeks access to, as awareness of the advantages of types of services is strongly determined by education. Data showed that education of the husband allows women to participate in various decisions within the household. Education also influences place of residence, owing to increased job opportunities and resultant higher socio-economic status. This in turn improves access to outside knowledge and information of both the husband and wife, which influences the women's bargaining strength within the household so that they participate in various household matters.

Occupation of the Respondents

Basu (1992) reports that in India, it has been found that women with greater autonomy are more likely to use antenatal and delivery care than women with lower autonomy. He also highlights that women's participation in gainful and visible employment improve their bargaining position within the household and is associated with greater gender equality in the distribution of household resources than when women are employed in invisible activities such as domestic work. Thus it can be assumed that a woman with independent financial resources will be able to exercise greater autonomy over her reproductive health. This becomes evident from the manner in which they seek ANC and PNC care. Mahapatro (2012) further adds that a woman with higher socio-economic status in terms of better education and employment has more autonomy than illiterate and unemployed women. 90% of the respondents in Assam were

unemployed/ housewives, 77% in Manipur, 65% in Meghalaya, and 66% in Sikkim. The other engagements were unskilled work, clerical jobs, small shops, farming, etc.

Total Monthly Income of the Family

In addition to education, income is another equally important determinant. We had noted earlier that Out of Pocket (OOP) expenditure on health is very high in the Indian scenario. Under such circumstances, purchasing power will play a vital role in choosing the preferred bundle of goods. Home deliveries thus cannot simply be attributed to lack of education and ignorance; where they feel institutional deliveries are not necessary. The other underlying reasons could range from no time to go to the health facility, distance, unavailability of transportation, and expenses. Besides determining access to healthcare facilities, family income also strongly determines another very important aspect for the woman and particularly, for an expectant mother and the new born baby. Deficiencies of certain nutrients are associated with maternal complications and deaths, foetal and new-born deaths, birth defects, and decreased physical and mental potential of the child. Thus monthly income also plays a great role in decision making related to actual utilisation of the type of RCH services.

The monthly income of all the participants were also quite low with several of them belonging to a family income group range of 1601-4809, with the highest being in Sikkim with 30%. Table 6 below presents the details. Regarding BPL cards, there were 20% in Assam, 22% in Manipur, 4% in

Meghalaya, and 38% in Sikkim amongst the respondents.

Table 5: Family Income

Monthly Income	AS	MN	ML	S K
	%	%	%	%
=> 1600	-	-	-	1.0
1601-4809	17.0	18.5	13.0	29.5
4810-8009	37.5	25.5	32.5	23.5
8010-12019	13.0	13.5	29.5	14.5
12020-16019	9.5	11.5	8.5	8.5
16020-32049	19.5	22.5	13.5	18.5
=> 32049	3.5	8.5	3.0	4.5
Total	100	100	100	100

Drinking Water

As far as source of drinking water was concerned, piped into dwelling, piped into plot, public tap, hand pump, bore well, protected well, protected spring, Lake/Pond/River/Canal, neighbourhood, purchased water, were the major sources. Piped into dwelling was highest in Meghalaya (18.1%) and Sikkim (10.5%). Overall, piped into plot was highest in all the states, with Sikkim leading the list (61.5%), followed by Manipur (35.5%), Assam (34.2%), and Meghalaya (28.6%). Public tap is the other source that is used by a majority of the people where it is 33.7% in Meghalaya, 15.5% in Sikkim, 14.1% in Assam and 10.5% in Manipur. Handpump is used 36.7% in Assam, whereas it almost non-existent in Manipur and Meghalaya. In Sikkim, it is totally non-existent.

With regard to water treatment, 97.5% use boiled water in Sikkim, 70% in Manipur, 64% in Meghalaya, and 27.5% in Assam. Filter method is used by 50% in Manipur, 47.5% in Assam, 23% in Meghalaya and 10.5% in Sikkim. Nobody was consuming untreated water in Sikkim, whereas it was as high as 41.5% in Assam, 21% in Meghalaya and 10% in Manipur.

Type of Housing

Several research have demonstrated that housing conditions are closely related to low income; insecure and low wage employment; and food insecurity suggesting that it is a cluster of disadvantages in living conditions that contribute to poor health (Shaw et al., 1999). Poor quality living circumstances act as social determinants of health, of which income and housing are the most obvious. The presence of stress and anxiety about their housing conditions creates overall distress (Bryant, 2008). Among women, most studies on health outcomes show that women who are economically and socially marginalized have poor health status and higher premature mortality than women with higher income (Auger & Alix, 2008). This understanding is significant in the context of this particular study. The type of house, numbers of bedrooms, separate kitchen, toilet etc. are strong socio-economic indicators and are discussed below.

There were 47% pucca houses in Sikkim, 27% in Assam, 22% in Manipur and 19% in Meghalaya. 66% houses were semi-pucca in Meghalaya, 29% in Assam, 42% in Manipur and 33% in Sikkim. Assam had the highest numbers of Kutcha houses (45%), followed by Manipur (37%), Sikkim (21%), and lastly Meghalaya 16%. There were also several respondents who had only two to three rooms in their houses, with Assam topping the list.

In this study, it was also found that overall only 28.50% houses were pucca in all the four states. This is quite minimal, despite the fact that the rural houses were not very much in the interiors, thereby giving a sense of semi-

urban location. Urban dwellings are assumed to be pucca in most instances. The Report on Housing Condition in India, 2002, No. 488, suggested that out of every 100 households in rural areas, 36 lived in pucca houses, 43 in semi-pucca houses and the rest in kutcha houses. On the other hand, out of every 100 households in urban areas, 77 lived in pucca structures, 20 in semi-pucca structures and only 3 in kutcha structures. In urban slums, 67% of the dwelling units were pucca. It also reported that Tripura, Manipur, Assam and Chhattisgarh were lagging considerably behind the national average in terms of households living in pucca houses. This is probably one of the reasons why there is a far greater proportion of kutcha and semi-pucca houses found in the present study. It is reiterated here that data was collected from 100 rural households and 100 urban households in each state.

Numbers of Rooms Including Kitchen

The respondents from Manipur were found to have greater numbers of rooms whereas a greater proportion of households in Assam and Sikkim were seen to have only one or two rooms. Regarding the overall status of the four states, 27.25% have five rooms or more, 21.13% have four rooms at least, 23.75% have minimum three rooms, 22.13% have two rooms and 5.75% have only one room. This indicates better standards of living. The data on family size showed 25.6% with only 3 family members, 29.1% with 4 members, 18.4% with 5 members and 11.6% with 6 members. The households with larger family members are much smaller and could be reflective of the joint families that have been included in

the study.

Respondents were asked about the numbers of rooms that were used for sleeping. This was included to help understand the socio-economic status of the respondents. Separate bedrooms especially for young couples provide privacy for discussions and decision making related to their reproductive preferences and practices. This will certainly influence maternal and child health and the overall health status of the family

Separate Kitchen

In developing countries, an estimated 4.1 million children under age five die from acute respiratory infections (ARI) every year (WHO 1995). In India, as in many other countries, ARI is the leading cause of childhood death (Murray and Lopez 1996). Mishra and Retherford (1997) point out that smoke from cooking increases the risks of ARIs in children. They further add that in India, women often cook under poorly ventilated conditions using pits or open U-shaped stoves, called chulhas. These stoves burn biomass inefficiently and release high volumes of noxious air pollutants indoors, which can have devastating repercussions, especially in the long run. Moreover, having a separate kitchen facilitates decision making in terms of food and nutrition requirements. In this study, overall across the four states, 92% have separate kitchens in their houses. Households are better off in this regard in Manipur amongst the 4 states while Sikkim is lagging behind.

Fuel Used for Cooking

Behera and Agarwal (2009) state that domestic cooking fuels are one of the important causes of indoor air pollution

and consequent health concerns particularly in developing countries. According to the SAARC India Country Report, 2013, more than 60% of Indian households depend on traditional sources of energy like fuel-wood, dung and crop residues for meeting their cooking and heating needs. In rural India, 85% of households use firewood or dung cakes as the primary source of energy for cooking (NSSO, 2007). Laxmiet. al. (2003) also argues that the type of fuel used for cooking is a strong determinant of the family's socio-economic status, which has a huge direct impact on the health of the women who do the cooking and other indoor activities of the household.

Nevertheless, it is a positive indicator that although majority of households (71.7%) fall under lower middle and lower class, a huge majority stated that they use LPG (62.5%) and electricity (24.3%). It was found that electricity is used for cooking by 43.5% in Sikkim, and 36.5 % in Manipur. It is minimal in the other two states. LPG is used for cooking by 81% in Sikkim, 65.5% in Manipur, 55% in Meghalaya, and 48.5% in Assam. Wood is used by 65.5% in Manipur, 58% in Assam, 48% in Meghalaya and 42.5% in Sikkim. Since the northeast region has abundant forestry, it is also seen that 53.5% are using wood. However, unless it is waste and dry twigs etc., using firewood for cooking must be sought to be minimised. Other sources such as bio-gas, charcoal, cow dung cake and agri-crop waste are also used but very minimally.

Type of Toilet Used

There is a direct relationship between water, sanitation and health. It is estimated that 1 in every 10 deaths in

India in villages, is linked to poor sanitation and hygiene. Open air defecation especially around water sources can pose a huge threat to the entire community's health. Human waste is full of dangerous bacteria that can cause diseases like cholera, typhoid, infectious hepatitis, polio, cryptosporidiosis, and ascariasis. When waste is not properly managed, it can come into contact with skin, water, insects and other things that ultimately transfer the bacteria back into the human body where it can make people sick (Pandey and Kumar, 2014). When general health and environment is not healthy, it is bound to affect maternal and child health too. According to Census 2001, 36.4% of the households in India had access to latrine which increased to 46.9% in Census 2011.

Another important thing that is closely related to health is about the types of toilet. There were 6% each with 'No facility/open' in Assam and Meghalaya and 1% each in Manipur and Sikkim. Regarding 'Flush/pour flush' there were 81% in Meghalaya, 77% in Sikkim, 75% in Manipur, and 49% in Assam. Pit latrines were used by 24% in Assam, 14% in Sikkim, 8% in Meghalaya and 7% in Manipur. Other options were exercised by 22% in Assam, 18% in Manipur, 9% in Sikkim and 5% in Meghalaya.

Pregnancy Registration and ANC Utilisation

It was found from data that women in the rural areas are more compliant in terms of ANC registration, availing of any ANC facilities and also in availing full ANC facilities as compared to their urban counterparts. This definitely hints at education not necessarily being

always a major factor of actually utilising ANC care. Availability, accessibility and the role of motivators would definitely also be significant factors. Registration facilities created by the Union Ministry at the sub-centres play an encouraging role. Another positive finding is that all those who registered for ANC availed full ANC services.

Regarding religion and its influence on utilisation of ANC, almost all the Hindus have utilised ANC services (only 1.4% says 'No'). Likewise, for all the other religions too, religion does not seem to have much influence on actual utilisation of ANC in these north-eastern states. A similar conclusion can be drawn in the case of caste too, where a clear majority irrespective of categories have registered as well as utilised full ANC. The concern arises in the case of BPL families, where 78.5% have not registered nor utilised and only 18.2% have done so.

Another aspect we can examine is about family type, where irrespective of family type, a clear majority has availed of ANC services. What is significant is that all the upper class households have utilised ANC fully while a few of the upper middle and lower middle households have not utilised such services. Moreover, the proportion of those who didn't utilise such services are relatively higher among the lower/ upper lower households. This means that economic affordability or purchasing power does play an important role in determining ANC utilisation.

Education is yet again another important variable where there are 1.1% of illiterate respondents who didn't utilise ANC. Contrastingly all post graduate respondents have utilised such services.

Likewise, her own age at marriage is significant as it was found that those who married above 18 years seem to show greater compliance with ANC. One more important observation was that women who have had greater numbers of children show greater compliance with ANC.

ANC Utilisation and IFA Consumption

Data was also collected about households that sought ANC services from Government setting, wherein they were classified as 'No ANC', 'Partial ANC' and 'Full ANC'. A similar representation was done for the private setting too. Data showed that there were respondents who completed full ANC by using a mix of government and private services. It was also found that irrespective of urban or rural dwelling, utilisation of government services are more. IFA consumption compliance was however relatively greater among rural households.

Regarding religion, caste, and type of family, it appeared that irrespective of the category they belong to, preference is for the government services. Moreover, among BPL families, it was seen that they strongly prefer government services as affordability is a major concern. Likewise, when observed against the other variables such as family type, socio-economic class, education of the respondents, husband's education, and wife's age at marriage, it was found that government services are preferred over private sector. The reason as stated earlier is that in northeast India, the private sector is not so evolved unlike in other more developed regions of India. It was also observed that IFA consumption was also

higher in the case of nuclear families, the middle/ lower middle and lower/ upper lower socio-economic class. Husband's education influenced IFA consumption to a large extent. It was seen that IFA was consumed for a period of upto three months or more among 59% households where husbands were educated; while where husbands were not educated, only 9.1% households consumed thus. Wife's age at marriage was also a strong determinant where 58.3% of those who were above 18 years consumed IFA tablets for more than 3 months, whereas only 9.9% of those below 18 years consumed it.

Type and Place of Delivery

There were more cases of normal deliveries in the rural areas while there were more institutional deliveries in the urban areas. This is of concern as one of the core agendas under the RCH programme was to encourage institutional deliveries. It needs to be examined as to whether it is mindset, economic constraints, or unavailability of facilities that are paramount in the choice of place of delivery. Religion did not have a significant influence on type of delivery or place of delivery. Caesarean delivery was observed more among the general category households while proportionately the SC households were seen to have opted more for non-institutional delivery. Less numbers of BPL households opted for caesarean delivery. However, majority of them have opted for institutional deliveries. A greater proportion of nuclear families have not opted for institutional deliveries. The upper class are seen to prefer caesarean and institutional delivery. The upper middle class also

showed more inclination towards caesarean delivery. Better educated respondents preferred normal and institutional delivery. Educated husbands as well as older women also seemed to prefer institutional delivery. Greater proportion of women with greater parity did not opt for institutional delivery.

Pregnancy and Delivery Complications

Data showed that there were relatively lesser pregnancy as well as delivery complications in the rural areas. Besides this, it was observed that religion, caste, BPL status or family type did not have much effect on pregnancy complications or delivery complications. Education also did not seem to affect complications much. Similar observations were made for age at marriage and parity.

JSY, PNC and Postnatal Complications

The numbers of JSY beneficiaries were found to be much more from rural areas. However, those utilising PNC services are more from the urban areas. Post natal complications also were marginally higher in the urban areas. Religion was not found to be a significant variable that influenced JSY access or PNC services and related complications. More of SCs and OBCs have accessed JSY. However, irrespective of JSY, STs and general category respondents have utilised PNC services. Post natal complications were quite high across all categories. 11.4% of BPL families have been left out of JSY while 24.3% of non-BPL families have availed of it. Surprisingly a greater proportion of non-BPL families have not availed of PNC. It was also found that family type does not influence access to

JSY and PNC, nor PNC complications. Another reassuring finding was that lower the economic class, greater was the utilisation of JSY services. A predictable finding that emerged was that lower and lower middle classes were utilising PNC services lesser than the upper and upper middle classes. Complications were also higher among the lower classes. A greater proportion of lesser educated respondents have got access to JSY facilities, presumably because they either belong to BPL families or to the relatively lower classes. Education also had a strong correlation with PNC where more of the better educated opted for it. A far greater proportion of educated husbands admitted to opting for ANC services. Greater proportion of respondents whose age at marriage is more than 18 have availed of JSY. Age at marriage was found to be an influential variable for PNC too. Although JSY is meant only for deliveries upto two children, it was found that 7.4% respondents with more than 3 children were getting this facility too. It was also found that PNC reduces with increased parity. However parity did not have much effect on post-natal complications.

Place of Delivery and Post Delivery Treatment

Regarding place of delivery, although overall government is preferred over private, there was not much variation across religious categories. Even 'other' options were exercised to quite an extent across religions in case of place of delivery besides government and private. However, in case of post-delivery treatments, majority opted for government followed by private. The

'other' option was almost nullified. Among all the caste categories, SCs and STs were seen to opt the least for private care and depended upon government and 'other' for deliveries. There was not much variation among BPL and non-BPL families about choice of place of delivery as well as post-delivery treatment. However, within the BPL families, almost all of them opted for Government and 'other' as preferred choices. Across family types too, government was the preferred place for both delivery as well as post-delivery treatment. Preference for delivery as well as treatment in private setting is proportionately higher in case of better socio-economic conditions. It was found that education influences choice of place of delivery where the respondents with higher education were seen to opt for private care to quite a large extent. This can be attributed to increased purchasing power. A similar thing was observed where husbands are uneducated and the preference for government setting is higher, which can once again be attributed to lack of purchasing power. When the wife's age at marriage is low, greater preference is shown for government setting.

Compliance and Preference for Antenatal Care

It is an important finding that there were far greater proportions of non-compliance with pre-natal check-up within the first 24 hours in the rural areas. More cases of death were also reported. In the rural areas, it was found that there a greater preference for ante-natal check up in the government setting. But what is disturbing is the prevalence of 'other' as a choice for neonatal check-up in both rural and urban, with a greater

prominence in rural areas. As observed earlier, religion does not play a major role in compliance with check-up or with place of check-up. There was an exception in the case of Christians, where it was observed that they were relatively less compliant as well as exhibited greater preference for government. Similarly another observation holds true in this case, where SCs are seen to be relatively less compliant with timely neo-natal check-up. However for choice of place, STs prefer government setting more as compared to the other categories. Surprisingly, there were greater proportion of non-BPL families who have not complied with timely check-up. Higher socio-economic class showed greater compliance and also preference for private care. Likewise higher education meant higher compliance and increased preference for private care. Husband's education also seemed to influence in a similar manner but since the sample was highly disproportionate (educated versus uneducated husbands), it is not easy to draw a definite conclusion. A similar explanation holds for wife's age at marriage where older women show more compliance. Another significant observation is that lower parity showed greater compliance with neonatal care. Lower parity also showed higher preference for private care.

Compliance with Immunization and Place of Immunization

There were more cases of 'partial' and 'no' immunization in the rural areas, which can be attributed to lack of awareness, poor facilities, and economic as well as domestic constraints. Religion, caste and family type were not found to be significant variables regarding

immunization. Proportionately, there was not much difference in compliance with immunization among BPL and non-BPL families for which the government health and family welfare programmes must be lauded. A noteworthy finding here was that despite higher socio-economic class, there were more cases of non-compliance with immunization. Education seemed to have a marginal positive influence on immunization. Similarly for wife's age at marriage and parity, the observation is not strongly conclusive as sample is disproportionate.

Conclusion

The findings of the study underline the significance of several socio-economic pointers in understanding the utilization of RCH services in the Northeast. For instance, education of both husband and wife were seen to be important determinants regarding place of delivery. On the other hand, religion did not have much influence on compliance with ante-natal check-up. In the rural areas, JSY is performing well but compliance with immunization is low in these areas. Thus to further boost the success of the RCH programme, the government must take into consideration the unique elements of the region and its people. The rural-urban differentials must also be noted. A thrust on education, and especially women's education; thus empowering them with awareness to take informed decisions besides of course, the undeniable aspect of economic empowerment is truly the way forward.

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